

CLASSIFICATION OF TEACHING, TEACHING PROCESSES AND THEIR INTERDEPENDENCE IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS.

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Annotation: Teaching is an activity encouraging various actions, organizational and practical activities organized with students in a planned and systematic manner in order to transform social behavior into a habitual form. Teaching is considered an effective tool at all stages of education and development of learners.

Key words: Reading, Teaching concept, Teaching process, Teaching, interest, activity, skepticism, evidence, awareness, strategies, inclination.

Reading is the process of learning, learning, thinking and creating specific actions of learners. In the process of studying, students learn unknown, unlearned information.

The concept of education is an expression of conscious activity aimed at mastering the set of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for living, living and working among people.

Teaching is an encouraging activity for various actions, organizational and practical activities organized in a planned and systematic way with students in order to transform social behavior into a habitual form. Teaching is considered an effective tool at all stages of education and development of learners.

The teaching process is a process that determines how the activities of the teacher and the learner will be in the educational process, how the educational process should be organized and conducted, and what actions the learners should perform in this process.

The quality and effectiveness of conducting the educational process largely depends on how well their organizers work in mutual relations. In this case, it will be necessary to develop the mechanisms for the correct organization of quality control of education on a scientific basis, and it will require the algorithmic justification of the factors determining the quality of education and the logical sequence of their use.

Among the factors that determine the quality of education, the following can be included with the components of the educational system in form 1:

- educators;
- DTS, curriculum and training programs;
- textbook, training manual, etc.;
- teaching tools;
- theoretical materials on subjects;
- practical materials on subjects;
- didactic materials on subjects;
- laboratory and workshop equipment;
- practices;
- information and communication technology tools.

Evaluating the content of pedagogical education and improving its quality and effectiveness is integrally dependent on each component (aspects, factors, indicators) related to the educational process, and therefore the pedagogical education system is considered a single dynamic system. In this sense, the organizers of the educational process can be expressed as follows (Figure 1):

1 - fig.

Organizational-structural scheme of the educational process.

Such an approach to the educational process consists in ensuring the fulfillment of the system of normative, organizational, educational-methodical, informational and material-technical conditions of personnel training. In this, the focus on teaching subjects will be strengthened.

Teaching of subjects is a process of education and improvement of teaching characteristics, which aims to form a scientific attitude and the following characteristics in the teacher:

- interest (desire to know) and activity (desire to do something to find out something);
- skepticism (willingness to scrutinize common thoughts);
- proofs (skills of using the logic and rules of proof in acquiring knowledge);
- awareness (the existence of a fund of information about the universe so that it is possible to think with its help);
- strategies (availability of search rules and willingness to use them);
- tendency (as a result of acquiring new knowledge, the educator begins to reconstruct his way of thinking about the world, placing the ideas and concepts of others on the same line based on the law).

So, the process of teaching subjects is the didactic basis of effective activity in the entire pedagogical process.

"The proposed project in the following form serves to ensure the effectiveness of pedagogical processes, which is considered to be the result of education and training processes, by ensuring the interdependence and connection of pedagogical processes"

The sequence of ensuring the effectiveness of pedagogical processes.

Seminars, practical and laboratory training in subjects during the educational process allow not only to strengthen theoretical knowledge and turn them into skills, but also to apply them in practical work. Such training corrects the feeling of confidence that the chosen profession is the right one.

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